

Synthesis and mesomorphic properties of azoester mesogens : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes

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Manuscript received 26 September 2006, revised 23 November 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : A new homologous series of azomesogens, 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes is synthesized. Mesomorphism commences from the very first homologue of the series and continues upto tetradecyl derivative. Last hexadecyl derivative is nonmesomorphic. All mesomorphic homologues are enantiotropic nematic. Thus, present homologous series is purely nematogenic. The usual odd-even effect is observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve. Transition curve behaves in a normal manner. The average thermal stability and mesomorphic characteristics are compared with structurally similar homologous series. Series is of middle ordered melting type without display of smectic character even in the last member of the series.

Keywords : Mesomorphism, nematic, liquid crystal, azomesogens, mesophase.

Introduction

Thermotropic liquid crystals are of great technological importance¹. Terminal and lateral substituents and geometrical shape of a molecule play an important role in mesomorphic properties of a mesogen. Generally, the terminal substituents comprise of either a homologue alkoxy or alkyl group or a compact unit such as nitro, cyano, halogen, etc.^{2,3}. A number of mesogenic homologous series of achiral esters with branched alkyl tail are also reported in the literature^{4,5}. A number of homologous series which have different molecular structures were synthesized by researchers earlier in order to establish the correlation between chemical constitution and mesomorphism⁶⁻¹⁰. Presently, we have synthesized a new homologous series comprising of -N=N- and -COO-central linkages.

Experimental

(1) 4-*n*-Alkoxy benzoic acids and 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were synthesized by the modified method of Dave *et al.*¹¹.

(2) 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl phenylazo-4'-methoxy benzene was prepared by known procedure¹². The azodye formed was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized in glacial acetic acid several times till constant melting point obtained, m.p. 133.0 °C. The yield is about 68.5%.

Table 1. Transition temperatures for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes

Sl. no.	<i>n</i> -Alkyl group	Transition temp. (°C)		
		Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1.	Methyl	–	138.0	247.0(d)
2.	Ethyl	–	90.0	251.0(d)
3.	Propyl	–	80.0	138.0
4.	Butyl	–	84.0	152.0
5.	Pentyl	–	65.0	158.0
6.	Hexyl	–	81.0	172.0
7.	Heptyl	–	83.0	142.0
8.	Octyl	–	92.0	147.0
9.	Decyl	–	81.0	130.0
10.	Dodecyl	–	86.0	124.0
11.	Tetradecyl	–	60.0	123.0
12.	Hexadecyl	–	–	89.0

(3) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy-benzoyloxy)-2-methylphenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes were synthesized by adding dropwise a solution of 4-hydroxy-2-methyl phenylazo-4'-methoxy benzene in pyridine to an ice cooled solution of respective 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chloride with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed for half an

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Fig. 1. 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes.

hour and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was acidified with 1 : 1 cold HCl and finally pure products were obtained by subsequent usual steps. The resulting products were purified by silica gel column chromatography using petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and ethyl acetate mixture (95 : 5) as eluent and crystallized by alcohol and benzene (80 : 20) until constant transition temperatures obtained and recorded in Table 1. Liquid crystalline properties were investigated on a Leitz Laboulux polarizing microscope with a heating stage. Analytical data supports the structure [Tables 2, 3(a) and 3(b)].

Results and discussion

4-Hydroxy-2-methyl phenylazo-4'-methoxy benzene is a non-liquid crystal substance but linking of phenyl ring bridged through -COO- and left *n*-alkoxy terminal induces mesomorphic character. Homologous series, 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes is entirely enantiotropic nematogenic except hexadecyl derivative, which is nonmesogenic. Smectic mesophase is totally absent for any members of the series.

The transition temperatures are plotted versus the number of carbon atoms in *n*-alkyl chain of the left *n*-alkoxy group from Table 1. Curves are drawn through the related points as shown in the Fig. 1. The solid-nematic or

solid-isotropic transition curve follows a zigzag path of rising and falling as series is ascended. Zigzag path of solid-nematic and nematic-isotropic transition curve is due to the sequential addition of -CH₂- methylene unit at the left *n*-alkoxy group. This causes differences in the length and linearity of the molecules and hence the difference in end to end intermolecular forces of attractions. It is directly related to magnitude of cohesive forces arising out of odd and even number of carbon atoms in *n*-alkoxy terminal. Thus overall end to end intermolecular forces of attractions are altered from homologue to homologue in the same series for odd and even member of the series. The nematic-isotropic transition curve for odd and even members of the series initially rises and thereafter falls up to the fourteenth homologue of the series in usual manner. First and second members of the series do not melt sharply at definite temperature but decomposes at higher temperatures. Usual odd-even effect is observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve. The texture of the nematic mesophase is threaded type as judged directly by observing the samples in a field of view of polarizing microscope. Thus, the present homologous series under discussion can be considered as middle ordered melting type with mesophase length minimum of 38.0 °C at the twelfth member and maximum of 161.0 °C at the second member of the series.

Table 2. Elemental analysis for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methyl phenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes

Sl. no.	<i>n</i> -Alkyl group	Molecular formula	% of Nitrogen	
			Calcd.	Obsd.
1.	Methyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	7.45	7.40
2.	Ethyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	7.18	7.11
3.	Propyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	6.93	6.90
4.	Butyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	6.70	6.78
5.	Pentyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄	6.48	6.41
6.	Hexyl	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₄	6.28	6.22
7.	Heptyl	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₄	6.09	6.14
8.	Octyl	C ₂₉ H ₃₄ N ₂ O ₄	5.91	5.89
9.	Decyl	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₂ O ₄	5.58	5.53
10.	Dodecyl	C ₃₃ H ₄₂ N ₂ O ₄	5.28	5.23
11.	Tetradecyl	C ₃₅ H ₄₆ N ₂ O ₄	5.02	5.09
12.	Hexadecyl	C ₃₇ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₄	4.78	4.71

Enantiotropic nematic property is shown from very first member of the series except last member of the series, due to the parallel orientations of molecules with end to end attractions in floating condition resisting thermal vibrations. Last member of the homologous series is nonmesogenic because of its high crystallizing tendency

(1) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methylphenylazo-4''-methoxy benzenes

(A) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methylphenylazo-4''-chloro benzenes¹³

(B) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methylphenylazo-4''-bromo benzenes¹⁴

(C) 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-2-methylphenylazo-4''-methyl benzenes¹⁵

Fig. 2

and the incapability of intermolecular cohesion forces to maintain parallel orientation in the floating condition or to form layered arrangement of molecules. Smectic mesophase is totally absent for all members of the present homologous series-I because of the extent of non-coplanarity caused by the molecules and resulted intermolecular forces of attractions are incapable to maintain layered arrangement of the molecules even in the monotropic condition. It is seen that nematic-isotropic transition curve shows alternation of transition temperatures from third to the eighth homologue but alternation diminishes as series is ascended because higher homologues are of even number and in case of higher homologues, the longer left *n*-alkyl chain of *n*-alkoxy group may be coiled or coupled to lie in the line with major axis of the core. Thus end to end contact would then ultimately be the same for odd and even homologue.

Table 3(a). Spectral data

Homologue	IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)	
Methyl	2934.0, 2846.0, 1462.0, 1375.2 cm ⁻¹ → alkyl group	
	1727.1, 1252.7 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- (ester group)	
	1595.0 cm ⁻¹ → -N=N- (azo group)	
	1559.3 cm ⁻¹ → -C=C- aromatic stre.	
	1142.7 and 1167.8 cm ⁻¹ → -O- (ether group)	
	839.9 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -sub. benzene ring	
	763.8 cm ⁻¹ → tri sub. benzene ring	
	IR confirms above structure	
	<i>n</i> -Dodecyl	2918.1, 2848.7, 1457.1, 1338.0 cm ⁻¹ → alkyl group
		1744.0, 1258.5 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- (ester group)
1602.0 cm ⁻¹ → -N=N- (azo group)		
1559.3 cm ⁻¹ → -C=C- aromatic stre.		
1144.7 and 1169.7 cm ⁻¹ → -O- (ether group)		
845.7 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -sub. benzene ring		
771.5 cm ⁻¹ → tri sub. benzene ring		
IR confirms above structure		

Table 3(b). Spectral data

Homologue	NMR spectra δ (ppm)
<i>n</i> -Butyl	0.98, (3H, t, -CH ₃)
	1.50 (2H, m, -CH ₂ -)
	1.82 (2H, m, -OCH ₂ -CH ₂ -)
	4.06 (2H, t, -OCH ₂ -)
	2.73 (3H, s, -PhCH ₃)
	3.90 (3H, s, -OCH ₃)
	6.90–8.17 (11H, m, Ar-H)
<i>n</i> -Pentyl	0.95 (3H, t, -CH ₃)
	1.41–1.46 (4H, m, 2 \times -CH ₂ -)
	1.81 (2H, m, -OCH ₂ -CH ₂ -)
	4.02 (2H, t, -OCH ₂ -)
	2.73 (3H, s, -PhCH ₃)
	3.89 (3H, s, -OCH ₃)
	6.90–8.17 (11H, m, Ar-H)

The mesomorphic characteristics of the title homologous series-I are compared with geometrically identical homologous series-A, B and C (Fig. 2). The homologous series-I, A, B and C possess three phenyl rings, linked through COO and N=N central bridges, left *n*-alkoxy terminal group at the *para* position with methyl group at *ortho* position to -N=N- unit at middle phenyl ring as common identical features, while they differ only by right functional terminal groups substituted at third phenyl ring. Therefore, mesogenic behaviour and degree of mesomorphism of the series under comparison is varied due to the variation of functional group or groups linked at the third phenyl ring only. These functional groups are -OCH₃, -Cl, -Br, and -CH₃ for series-I, A, B and C respectively. They differ in size, polarity, polarizability and affecting planarity of molecules as well as creation of steric hindrance, in addition to other factors, responsible for intermolecular forces of cohesion. Thus variation of intermolecular forces of cohesion and end to end attractions are directly related to mesomorphic behaviour and degree of mesomorphism. The average thermal stabilities of series-I, A, B and C are given in Table 4. Nematic-isotropic average thermal stability of homologous series-I is the highest amongst the group of homologous series-I, A, B and C (Table 4). Relatively the highest polarity and polarizability of terminally attached -OCH₃ functional group with respect to -Cl, -Br, and -CH₃, raised the intermolecular forces of attractions, and hence resulting into highest nematic-isotropic thermal stability. Late commencement of occurrence of nematic mesophase in case of series-B and C, i.e. the series with -Br and -CH₃ terminals may be due to their bigger size, steric hindrance and lower polarity affecting end to end intermolecular forces of attractions; incapable of maintaining parallel orientations of molecules in floating condition increasing

crystallizing tendency of early homologues. Extent of coplanarity caused by molecules of series-I is not enough to maintain layered arrangement of the molecules and hence smectic mesophase does not occur even upto the last homologue. Therefore relative average thermal stability for the smectic does not require to be discussed. The study suggests the following terminal group efficiency order for nematic, on the basis of thermal stability as under,

Table 4. Average thermal stabilities

Series	Average transition temp. (°C)			
	Series-(I) (-OCH ₃)	Series-(A) (-Cl)	Series-(B) (-Br)	Series-(C) (-CH ₃)
Nematic-isotropic or	162.18	142.0	139.0	103.9
Isotropic-nematic Commencement of nematic phase	(C ₁ -C ₁₄) C ₁	(C ₁ -C ₁₆) C ₁	(C ₄ -C ₁₆) C ₄	(C ₃ -C ₁₆) C ₃

Conclusion :

The synthesis of new mesogenic homologous series of azoester derivatives is carried out. All the members of the series exhibit enantiotropic nematic mesomorphism with absence of smectic property. The average thermal stability of present homologous series-I is higher than those of structurally related compounds, which can be attributed to the high polarity and polarizability of the molecule, due to -OCH₃ terminal.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to present and Ex-Head of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Vadodara, for their valuable co-operation. Also we are thankful to the Director, Central Salts and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar for the analysis of samples.

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